

Fig S11. Collection of three *D. discoideum* tracks driven by the standard amoeboid type of cell motion with corresponding kymographs: Local motion, relative fluorescence intensity, the underlying protrusion component inferred from our model, and the contour area. For each cell track, the 1st percentile of the individual area time series (last row) was chosen as the reference area (gray dashed line) in our model: 62.43 , 122.99 , and $64.61 \mu\text{m}^2$, respectively. The model weights (w_{prot} , w_{APCSF} , w_{AAF}) were estimated individually for each cell track: $(4.513, 0.023, 0.902)$, $(4.513, 0.048, 1.429)$, and $(6.505, 0.070, 0.676)$, respectively from **(A)** to **(C)**.